

Multi-Structure Product Data Management in Ship Design

Dawid Stade, CONTACT Software, Bremen/Germany, dawid.stade@contact-software.com

Maximilian Idjen, CONTACT Software, Bremen/Germany, maximilian.idjen@contact-software.com

Elisabeth Brandenburg, CONTACT Software, Bremen/Germany, elisabeth.brandenburg@contact-software.com

Abstract

In shipbuilding, documentation, plans, and drawings are typically the primary deliverables. Despite the absence of a unified "single ship model", digitalisation facilitates the connection of these documents to a digital product model. Traditional product data models are the outcome of the ability to organise components into assemblies, which is represented by a hierarchical structure. However, the varying demands throughout a ship's lifecycle and the complexity of the vessel necessitate extensions to this. Thus, an interconnected data model comprising spatial, system-oriented, and engineering-oriented structures is proposed to accommodate planning information and to offer different views on information objects for multiple disciplines. As it is validated on practical requirements, this enhances the shipbuilding process by providing a holistic representation of the ship.

1. Introduction

As in other industries, ship design is undergoing continuous digitalisation, dating back to the 1970s. Early developments, such as the adoption of computer-aided design, have culminated in the current era of smart digitalisation. Nowadays, naval architects and engineers are provided with tools and methods that enhance the efficiency of design and, moreover, elevate its quality over the entire life cycle. These encompass, for instance, the parametric generation and optimisation of hull forms, as well as simulation-driven ship design, *Papanikolaou et al. (2024)*.

The SEUS project, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101096224>, was initiated with the objective of promoting the digitalisation of shipbuilding. The overarching aim of the project is to establish a connection between the domains of design, simulation and optimisation applications for shipbuilding and the Product Lifecycle Management (PLM) realm. A European consortium of shipyards, CAD and PLM vendors, and research institutions is implementing a platform that integrates CAD and PLM processes, specifically designed for the shipbuilding industry.

Ship design is typically project-driven and tender-based. In comparison to other industries, batch sizes are commonly small. The sheer size of a ship poses a challenge, resulting in an enormous quantity of information that arises during design. For instance, for one icebreaker vessel, up to 60,000 documents and drawings, 100,000 issues and 150,000 components require storage, organisation and management. The biggest vessels, such as aircraft carriers, easily surpass 1,000,000 parts. These objects occur at different design phases and have their own life cycles. Ship complexity presents another key challenge, especially in European shipbuilding, which focuses on highly specialised vessels, *Kamola-Cieslik (2021)*. Ship design is confronted with diverse vessel types, numerous and varied requirements, a complex process of requirement elucidation, additional non-economic and non-operational demands, and ambiguous engineering responsibilities. Consequently, ships are classified as physically large and complex systems, with a design process being akin to civil engineering rather than to the development of smaller vehicles, such as cars, *Andrews (2013)*.

Van Den Hamer and Lepoeter (1996) delineate five dimensions of product data management: views and hierarchies, versions and statuses, as well as product variants. The former are also designated as a taxonomy, which comprises a hierarchical decomposition of the product data and corresponding perspectives. To address the aforementioned challenges in ship design, diverse perspectives are employed, contingent upon the specific design phase and domain. While, for example, functional views

are required in early ship design, production planning demands spatial views, dividing the vessel into zones in which the ship is to be manufactured, *Aragão Fonseca et al. (2023)*. Furthermore, multiple disciplines within the domains are dependent on updates and information from each other in real time. The corresponding hierarchical structures need to organise product data adequately.

A conventional taxonomy, such as that offered by the majority of Product Lifecycle Management (PLM) systems, hierarchically divides the product into assemblies and components. Its layers are reflected by relationships between the elements that can be designated as “is part of” or “consists of”. The standard taxonomy fails to satisfy shipbuilding demands. Therefore, this study aims to propose a data model capable of addressing the multifaceted requirements of the ship design process. Given the absence of standardised practices and the resultant heterogeneity in ship design implementations across European shipyards, the proposed model must also exhibit the flexibility to accommodate diverse procedural variations, *Bronson et al. (2024)*. The presented data model is implemented within and specifically for CONTACT Elements, a modular and flexible Product Lifecycle Management system.

2. Related Literature and Research

Ship design encompasses the entirety of a vessel's life cycle. The development process can be segmented into discrete phases, *Papanikolaou (2010)*. The process commences with the conceptual design phase, which *Andrews (2013)* describes as follows: Following a solicitation of bids by the prospective owner, the shipyard is required to respond within a constrained timeframe, occasionally as short as six weeks. The proposal must encompass a technically viable concept, detailed cost projections, and a development and construction schedule. The actual approach highly depends on the novelty of the ship being developed. However, in commercial shipping, shipyards' financial risk encourages evolutionary development. This involves exploration, concept studies, as well as concept design and selection. Initially, a preliminary and broadly distributed analysis is conducted to ascertain the feasibility of achieving the stipulated requirements. This usually results in several concepts in which questions of exploration are clarified in greater depth. In the subsequent concept development, decisions such as the selection of the ship style, equipment and performance characteristics are made iteratively. With the help of a synthesis model, the ship size and architecture are determined and evaluated. In this early phase, a functional view of the ship is often used, such as the Ship Work Breakdown Structure (SWBS) and the Skipsteknisk Forskningsinstitut (SFI) Group system, *Bronson et al. (2024)*. They divide the ship into elements such as the hull structure, propulsion unit, power generation, auxiliary systems, equipment and furniture.

In the following contractual design phase, all necessary documents for the contract's conclusion must be prepared and agreed on. These include essential drawings, material and equipment lists, as well as detailed specifications. Additionally, a schematic representation of all systems is provided, including the main drive, pipeline systems, electrical systems, and cargo systems, *Misra (2015)*.

With the signing of the contract, the detailed design begins, in which, according to its name, a fine-grained definition and evaluation of the design take place. Furthermore, a detailed planning of the production of the ship takes place, for which, in addition to the aforementioned functional views, those that are suitable for the production of the ship come into focus, *Aragão Fonseca et al. (2023)*. For example, the ship is divided into grand blocks, decks, spatial objects and zones, depending on the discipline, each containing all manufactured and installed components within that area. An example of such a hierarchical view is the Product Work Breakdown Structure, *Pal (2015)*.

In the construction phase, individual steel plates are manufactured and assembled into blocks and grand blocks after preparatory measures. Before these are erected and welded for assembly to the entire ship, the most extensive assembly of the heaviest and largest components, such as the main engines, takes place, as this is comparatively easy in this state. After the composition of the grand blocks and blocks, the remaining equipment, including all modules and interior components, is installed.

During the operation, functional views are again in the foreground, offering a wealth of detail on systems, subsystems, components, modules and parts, *Aragão Fonseca et al. (2023)*. The precise identification of the equipment contained in the views is given, for example, by the aforementioned SFI Group System. With the reaching of the end of life of a ship, the decommissioning is in the foreground, which can consist of a refit, re-commissioning, sale or scrapping. In the case of scrapping, the product structure should list all those components that need to be decommissioned. In addition, information on toxic or hazardous materials must be included, *Andrade et al. (2015)*.

Among the approaches to cope with these requirements by a PLM system, the Fourth-Generation Design (4GD) should be emphasised. 4GD aims to combine an effective virtual design environment with comprehensive product data management. It consists of a flat product hierarchy consisting of design elements that organisational partitions can group. This approach allows different taxonomies to be mapped. However, as *Levišauskaitė et al. (2017)* report, this approach cannot achieve an effective improvement in the reuse of 3D models.

3. Core Elements of the proposed data model

Taking into account the size and complexity of a ship, different views on a ship's product data are required depending on the design domain and phase. These comprise functional and spatial views, each requiring a hierarchical data structure.

Fig.1: Core elements of the proposed shipbuilding PLM data model

Fig.1 shows an abstract representation of the structures, customisable for specific use cases. The functional structure depicted on the left can be implemented, for instance, as an instantiation of the SFI Group System. The spatial structure, along with the functional structure, can be subsumed under the overarching concept of model or design. Overall, the different uses of the structures highlight the overlap between shipbuilding and factory planning characteristics. The industry-neutral model emphasises the significance of functional and spatial structures in factory planning, providing the foundation for related perspectives. A design is employed in shipyards for the iterative development and construction of similar vessels. Consequently, a design functions as a template, encompassing critical spatial and functional architectures, incorporating varying levels of detailed information.

The right-hand side of the figure depicts structures exclusively employed during the instantiation of a model or design, specifically the development of a particular vessel. The manufacturing structure primarily facilitates the planning of steel construction for grand blocks and blocks of a ship, which

contain the items which are linked to production steps in the WBS. The organisational structure serves to coordinate cross-structural elements to form so-called production modules (collections), which are in turn pre-built components.

To emphasise the project-driven nature of ship and factory development, a product data model always refers to a corresponding main project. The project allows for organising development tasks, deliverables, milestones, phases and production activities, but is not within the primary focus of this work. It may encompass a range of sub-projects and tasks, all of which can be associated with product data. Further functionalities, such as open points and checklists, are also available. The incorporation of external project management applications is also feasible.

3.1. Hierarchical structures and corresponding views

As previously indicated, the development of a ship necessitates diverse perspectives, depending on the specific development domain and phase. These views require a corresponding hierarchy, mapped by the data model.

System structure: A vessel typically comprises multiple systems. Each system generally encompasses a significant quantity of elements, which can be hierarchically organised into system item groups. The relationships between the layers of a system can be described as "is part of" or "consists of". Based on Fig.1, specific system structures can be implemented. The SFI Group System, for instance, is widely adopted in the European shipbuilding industry.

Spatial structure: A spatial structure offers the possibility to represent the ship in a spatially structured way. Given the heterogeneity of spatial object types, such as compartments, rooms, decks or zones, a multiplicity of spatial structures may exist. Furthermore, hybrid structures are also implementable. Since a system usually extends over several spatial objects, system item groups or items can be assigned to multiple spatial objects. Relationships between the layers of a spatial structure can be interpreted as "includes" or "is located in".

Manufacturing Structure: The manufacturing structure is closely related to the spatial structures, but is specific to the planning of steel construction in shipbuilding, such as the construction of grand blocks and blocks. It is also used to plan the assembly of large items/components in the context of the blocks. Individual items and modules are assigned to the production steps by assigning them to blocks. This assignment is then used to generate block-specific component BOMs for production and procurement, as well as the building methodology for the assembly of the blocks and grand blocks. Relationships between the structural levels can also be described here as "includes" or "is located in".

Module Structure: The module structure enables the free organisation of information objects. In contrast to the structures mentioned above, these objects do not require structural purity. Elements from various structures can be aggregated and displayed through the hierarchical structuring of item collections. Freely structuring and linking objects is a practical necessity, for example, in the planning phase for the pre-assembly of main modules, such as externally assembled funnels, cabins, or mission equipment, where cross-structural linkages are essential. Using an item collection, the items from different systems are combined into a module and can be linked to spatial and manufacturing objects for further planning.

3.2. Items and related entities

An item is part of a system and can also be referred to as a functional location. It acts as a placeholder containing important meta information, such as requirements, a specific shipbuilding ID, such as an SFI Code, and location-specific metadata. E.g., the need for a pump component may be identified early in development, but its specific selection is deferred until later in the process. Accordingly, an item can refer to a supplier-specific component, which in turn can be selected from a component catalogue. This combination aims to increase the reuse of components, such as parts at different locations of a ship.

With document management being an integral part of ship design, items can be linked to documents, which have their own lifecycle and relationships, such as project tasks. Therefore, for example, the supplier contract for the procurement of a component for a functional location can be managed. Issues represent another key relationship, especially during ship construction. They document and track problems and improvements in construction, acceptance, and operation, enabling controlled resolution. Further item relationships are configurable per application.

4. Concrete Data Model Implementation

The presented data model was successfully implemented in the shipbuilding platform WAVE based on the Technology CONTACT Elements for both a partner and an external customer. At the system level, WAVE utilises the SFI system, which enables the clear identification of items and modules across disciplines and tools. For a better overview, compartments and rooms are also structured via decks and zones. Furthermore, the module structure is extended with BOM elements for the handling of prefabricated components with their respective foundations. Fig.2 illustrates the resulting data model, which consists of the view-specific object extensions and additional relationships.

Fig.2: Concrete data model implementation in the WAVE shipbuilding platform

The implementation only includes elements and attributes from the Basic and Detail Design phase. More in-depth analysis already shows that milestones and delivery data from project management must be comprehensively linked with the elements to ensure smooth planning of the subsequent phases. For this purpose, CAD documents were supplemented with planning-relevant attributes, such as the delivery date, and integrated directly into the work breakdown structure as deliverables. Therefore, this approach can be utilised to plan and design externally fabricated modules efficiently. In addition to extracting block-specific BOMs, this also requires linking to module-specific 2D CAD drawings. The resulting elements are then used as functional components inside blocks and are connected to production steps within the building methodology for the grand block as part of the manufacturing process. With the following release versions, ship designs, full support for the SWBS, and the mapping of sister ships will be integrated into WAVE. Initial analyses have shown that the data model is only limited by missing attributes and elements, such as a ship type, which must be added and supplemented with PLM standard objects.

5. Discussion

The suggested multi-structure data model for a PLM system in shipbuilding allows for the creation of multiple functional and spatial structures to organise product data across all design phases and involved disciplines. A project structure, a fundamental element in shipbuilding, is not maintained in parallel with the product structure. Instead, it can be linked to individual data elements and is therefore interconnected with the key elements in the data model. This integrated methodology facilitates, for instance, document management, a critical aspect of shipbuilding. With the presented approach, Documents can be managed in the context of both product and project hierarchies.

Furthermore, CONTACT Elements, as the basis of the data model, features an open and modular platform. This design enables the system's adaptation to different application scenarios. A shipyard or design firm lacking prior experience with PLM systems can adopt a phased implementation approach. This approach involves initially transferring only partial processes or data, such as specific design phases. Conversely, the platform and data model enable integration of external expert tools, for example, simulations or CAD applications. The design processes can be progressively adapted for implementation within the PLM framework. Simultaneously, the PLM system can function as the Single Source of Truth from the beginning. Employee acceptance, specifically the initial recognition of added value, poses a significant challenge in PLM system implementation and digitalisation in general. For this reason, the data in the system should be labelled according to the terminology common in shipbuilding and training of the affected employee groups is of central importance. This problem constitutes an integral component of the SEUS project and is subject to further examination, as exemplified by the work of *Tacgin and Martinsuo (2025)*.

While the proposed data model presents notable advantages for shipbuilding applications, comprehensive validation remains outstanding. The solution presented herein represents an interim finding, requiring further research for completion. For this purpose, a functional validation will be carried out using both theoretical use cases and practical applications of European shipyards. Essential criteria are complete data integrity, ensuring the required interlinking of all information, and efficient information retrieval.

The data model maps shipbuilding's development phases, enabling linked, centralised information management. Although in the literature consulted, discrepancies with reality can be found in the course of the shipbuilding phases presented, the incorporation of additional data domains remains a plausible consideration. For example, *Aragão Fonseca et al. (2023)*, did not mention the basic design phase, although essential systemic foundations are developed within it. As reported by *Bronson et al. (2024)*, planning and process data domains are requisite in shipbuilding to effectively manage administrative and technical processes throughout the vessel's development and manufacturing phases. The same applies to the human domain, which includes the relevant people in development and production. Finally, the implementation of a Digital Twin in the context of a fleet management system, representing a comprehensive mapping of the ship's operational parameters, also justifies consideration. These developments may be part of further research with a focus on the interaction of data domains.

6. Summary and Outlook

This paper proposes a multi-structure data model for a shipbuilding PLM system. It integrates core spatial and functional elements for linking and organising product information. Adaptability to diverse development domains and phases simplifies the design of physically large and complex systems such as ships. In addition, these entities are interconnected with elements of project management, reflecting the project-driven nature inherent in ship development.

The data model, in conjunction with its target platform, CONTACT Elements, facilitates flexible adjustments to diverse circumstances. Since the introduction of a comprehensive PLM system may pose significant challenges, the model and associated platform offer the possibility of successive integration, which nevertheless already allows the provision of a single source of truth.

The current study represents an interim report, and comprehensive validation remains outstanding. A functional evaluation is planned based on theoretical and practical application scenarios derived from European shipyards. The implementation of the presented data model within SEUS has already yielded promising results. A final validation can only take place after the complete implementation across all phases. Central elements are the evaluation of data integrity and information retrieval. The integration of further information domains is to be considered. E.g., service planning and process information, and a human domain for administrative and technical processes, warrant further research. In addition, further questions arise from the interactions between existing and new domains, which can lead to entirely new research topics. All in all, multi-structure management provides the basis for making complexity in shipbuilding manageable and is therefore a promising approach for further research.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101096224.

References

- ANDRADE, S.L.; MONTEIRO, T.G.; GASPAR, H.M. (2015), *Product Lifecycle Management In Ship Design: From Concept To Decommission In A Virtual Environment*, ECMS, pp.178–184
- ANDREWS, D. (2013), *The True Nature of Ship Concept Design – And What it Means for the Future Development of CASD*, COMPIT Conf., Cortona, pp.33–50
- ARAGÃO FONSECA, Í., FERRARI DE OLIVEIRA, F., GASPAR, H.M. (2023), *Open Framework for Digital Twin Ship Data: Case Studies on Handling of Multiple Taxonomies and Navigation Simulation*, Int. J. Maritime Eng. 165(A1), pp.23–42
- BRONSON, J.A.; LUZ, F.H.P.; FONSECA, I.A.; GASPAR, H.M. (2024), *Graph databases for multi-domain taxonomies in maritime systems*, ECMS, pp.250–257
- KAMOLA-CIESLIK, M. (2021), *Changes in the Global Shipbuilding Industry on the Examples of Selected States Worldwide in the 21st Century*, Eur. Research Studies J. XXIV(Issue 2B), pp.98-112
- LEVIŠAUSKAITĖ, G.; ULSTEIN, B.A.; GASPAR, H. (2017), *4GD Framework in Ship Design*, 16th COMPIT Conf., Cardiff
- MISRA, S.C. (2015), *Design Principles of Ships and Marine Structures*, CRC Press
- PAL, M. (2015), *Ship work breakdown structures through different ship lifecycle stages*, Int. Conf. Computer Applications in Shipbuilding, Bremen
- PAPANIKOLAOU, A. (2010), *Holistic ship design optimisation*, Computer-Aided Design 42(11), pp.1028–1044
- PAPANIKOLAOU, A.; BOULOUGOURIS, E.; ERIKSTAD, S.O.; HARRIES, S.; KANA, A.A. (2024), *Ship Design in the Era of Digital Transition: A State-of-the-Art Report*, IMDC Conf.
- TACGIN, Z.; MARTINSUO, M. (2025), *An augmented reality solution for digitalisation training in shipbuilding: Systematic review and application development*, 19th INTED Conf., Valencia, pp.1997–2011
- VAN DEN HAMER, P.; LEPOETER, K. (1996), *Managing design data: The five dimensions of CAD frameworks, configuration management, and product data management*, Proc. IEEE 84(1), pp.42–56